

Research Analysis Identifier System

Enabling Data Analysis without Data Sharing

RAISE creates **Innovative Services and Outputs** to support **trustworthy research** and **data analysis services** based on **crowdsourced distributed resources** along with local resources.

- **Research Analysis Identifier (RAI):** a **unique identifier** of any result along with the dataset information and the **processing script** (RAI Registration Service), without disclosing any source code or raw data.
- **RAI Certified nodes:** A trustworthy crowdsourced network offering data storing and processing resources (community resources).
- **RAI Cloud:** Orchestrates the data sharing, processing, and finding.
- **Dataset plagiarism identification and dataset proof-of-origin services**
- **RAI Synthetic Data Generator** and the **RAI SDK** to help researchers develop processing scripts by getting access to sample, small scale datasets which mock real data.

Applied in:

Health

Mobility

Environment

Cross-disciplinary

Total Budget: € 4,836,125.00

Project duration: 40 months

Start Date: 1 October 2022

Project Coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis,
Lab of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation, AUTH

Contact Us: info@raise-science.eu

[raise.science](https://www.raise-science.eu)
[@RaiseScience](https://twitter.com/RaiseScience)
[raise.science](https://www.raise-science.eu)
 zenodo RAISE EOSC project
www.raise-science.eu

Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.